

Advances in self-healing coatings based on Diels-Alder chemistry

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ABSTRACT

Dynamic covalent polymer networks based on the Diels-Alder (DA) cycloaddition between furan and maleimide represent powerful and highly investigated tools in the design of self-healing coatings. In this minireview the most recent demonstrations of repairable coatings based on such platform chemistry are comprehensively discussed. In particular, the trends in the synthesis of DA networks, the enhancement of properties and advanced coating applications over the last ten years are highlighted. Furthermore, the current challenges in terms of the sustainability of DA coatings, performance assessment and the technological feasibility of healing procedures are outlined in the context of a future large-scale implementation.

1. Introduction

Polymer coatings are ubiquitous in daily life. Being used for protection and aesthetic purposes, the global industry for these materials continues to grow with an expected value of 16.2 billion in 2031 [1]. Currently, common organic coatings are based on acrylic, epoxy, polyurethane, polyester and fluoropolymers. These materials must be replaced completely after failure, resulting in high costs and energy requirement. In contrast, self-healing polymer coatings could significantly extend the service life, which is why they have received much attention lately. Some self-healing coatings can repair themselves upon damage without any human intervention (autonomous healing) [2]. Others may need an external stimulus, such as light or heat, to induce healing (non-autonomous). In addition, self-healing can be extrinsic or intrinsic. Extrinsic self-healing involves external agents such as capsules and vascular networks, which release a healing agent at the damaged site [3]. Intrinsic self-healing does not require these, and is brought to the material by introducing reversible interactions into the polymer matrix itself. These interactions can be either dynamic covalent bonds or non-covalent, such as hydrogen bonding or ionic interactions. Regardless of their type, they give rise to rigidity, but their dynamic nature provides enough (temporary) flexibility for polymer chains to diffuse into the damaged site [4].

Some reviews have covered the mechanisms and methods to design self-healing coatings. Utrera-Barrios and co-workers provided a rigorous overview of work that has been done on combining multiple self-healing mechanisms [5]. Recently, Beach et al. discussed the progress in organic coatings in general, with an interesting discussion on the future

perspective of organic coatings [6]. Cheng and co-workers elaborated on the mechanisms behind crack closure, including a more detailed discussion about the perspective towards applications [3]. Guo focused more on UV assisted self-healing coatings and concluded that research about self-healable coatings is still ongoing, and that the high price of building blocks and the complex synthesis pathways mainly prevent upscaling of self-healing coatings [7].

When considering dynamic covalent bonds that facilitate intrinsic self-healing abilities, the [4 + 2] cyclo-addition between furan and maleimide (Fig. 1) is regarded as one of the more appealing chemistries. Better known as the Diels-Alder (DA) reaction, it has been used to develop recyclable thermosets since the first demonstration of the concept in 2002 [8]. The forward 'click' reaction between furan and maleimide occurs at lower temperatures until around 70 °C, while the retro-Diels-Alder (rDA) dominates the equilibrium above 100 °C.

The dynamic character of the reaction between furan and maleimide at such moderate temperatures has led to many publications reporting self-healing coatings with DA as foundation for the self-healing feature [5,6]. In addition, the versatility to synthesize systems with this chemistry from biobased precursors contributed to its popularity as well [9]. An overview of recent applications of DA-based coatings is presented in Fig. 1, along with strategies how to assist damage repair. The applicability on a commercial scale can be increased by two strategies, with inclusion of Near-IR (NIR) responsive nanoparticles, or by including molecules that react on mechanical damage to allow for easier damage detection on coatings.

In this mini-review, we intend to highlight in detail the advances in coatings based on DA chemistry, and the perspective for each

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application they are considered for. DA coatings have not been specifically reviewed in the last ten years. With comparisons between recent studies in self-healing conditions, efficiency and material strength, we shed light on the current state of DA coating research, and its outlook to replace conventional polymer coatings within the scope of various applications.

2. Design of DA networks

2.1. Epoxy-based networks

Thermally induced healing based on DA in epoxy-based coatings was originally reported by Liu et al. more than a decade ago [10]. Inspired by the seminal work of Wudl [8] the polymer network was obtained by the DA-coupling in solution of low molecular weight tri-furan and trismaleimide compounds. Their synthesis entailed the modification of epoxy precursors like furfuryl glycidyl ether (FGE) and diglycidyl ether of Bisphenol A (DGEBA) with furfurylamine (FA).

Recent works are still largely based on similar widely available building blocks, including the 1,1'-(methylene-4,1-phenylene) bismaleimide (DPBM). Nevertheless, the polymer network design has shifted from using small furan-functional molecules [11] (Fig. 2a) towards furan-functionalized macromolecules reacted with DPBM [12–16] (Fig. 2b) or trismaleimides [17], in order to better tailor properties demanded by specific applications. For example, commercial polyetheramines (amino-terminated polyethylene glycols) can be easily capped with furan groups using FGE and then crosslinked with DPBM, resulting in coatings with mechanical properties ranging from thermoset to elastomers, according to the length of the polyether backbone [12, 16]. In addition, substituting DPBM with a telechelic, maleimide-terminated polyether allows to avoid the usage of solvents in the coating fabrication [18].

Nevertheless, when barrier properties against corrosion, such as reduced permeability to water and ions, are targeted, densely cross-linked networks are preferred [19]. In this context, the reaction between DGEBA and FA constitutes a straightforward approach to densely furan-functionalized oligomers for subsequent DA coupling with DPBM [15,20]. In particular, Fang et al. [15] investigated those systems and reported slightly superior anticorrosion properties compared to DGEBA (irreversibly) cured with diamine. In the same study, thermal healing was also observed in hybrid epoxy networks, *i.e.* including both amine-cured and DA-crosslinked DGEBA. In a work from the same group [20] an amino-silane was included in the same DA matrix in order to increase the wetting ability of the coating and thus contributing to healing of wide scratches.

Aiming at increasing dimensional stability at the healing

temperatures, Amendola et al. developed a hybrid epoxy network with anticorrosion features by using a different synthetic strategy (Fig. 2c). An epoxy-terminated DA adduct was first obtained by coupling DPBM with FGE [14,21] and then combined with DGEBA and simultaneously cured with a diamine.

2.2. Polyurethanes

Polyurethanes (PU) are generally synthesized from the addition of di- or (tri-)isocyanates and polyols. The chemical design of DA functional PUs relies on the high reactivity of isocyanate groups which are usually reacted with FA, furfuryl alcohol (or diols). Analogous to the epoxy coatings, two general approaches are followed in the synthesis of DA-based PU coatings. The first one entails the synthesis of linear furan-functional PUs followed by its coupling with a bismaleimide like DPBM [13,22–26] while in the second one, a DA adduct diol, is first synthesized by coupling a hydroxyl-functional maleimide with furfuryl alcohol, and then embedded in the PU matrix as reversible crosslinker [27–35].

Notably, Feng et al. [23] coupled a difunctional, furan-ended PU, with a DPBM resulting in a linear PU with higher healing ability than a conventional thermoplastic PU extended with butanediol. Nonetheless, DA polymer networks require multifunctional furan PUs, which are typically obtained by reacting isocyanate with furan diols. Different studies expanded the library of those compounds, mostly biobased, and investigated the effect of substituents on the thermal reversibility and healing of the obtained coatings after crosslinking with DPBM [24–26].

The “adduct approach” (Fig. 2c), *i.e.* the use of a DA adduct as building block, ideally offers a more precise control on the amount of furan-maleimide adducts in the network, which is formed in a subsequent step through polyaddition or polycondensation. Conversely, when DA coupling is used to form the network, early vitrification can hinder full conversion of furan and maleimide groups [36]. In addition, functional DA adducts represent an interesting alternative to the usage of DPBM linker [27–29,31–33,35]. For example, Sung et al. [27] combined a diol-functional DA adduct with a polyisocyanate and acrylic polyol, obtaining a material compliant with mechanical and aesthetic properties of automotive coatings. Interestingly Farschchi et al. [28] combined a similar diol with commercial polyester/polyisocyanate to obtain a healable powder coating, formulated without the use of solvents. In other studies, the DA adduct was used to achieve healing properties in waterborne [22,29,31] or UV-curable [30,32,33] formulations.

The DA links are mostly placed in the “hard segments” of the PU chains, possibly hindering the healing ability at mild temperature of those networks. In this context, Truong et al. [35] proposed a new design which entails DA links at the interface between soft (polycaprolactone)

Fig. 1. An overview of potential applications for which the DA reaction has been considered in recent literature. The reversible reaction of furan and maleimide towards adducts can form reversible crosslinks, as illustrated in the middle.

Fig. 2. Major synthetic strategies used to build DA polymer networks from a furan precursor containing an amino, epoxy, hydroxyl or double bond functionality: (a) Modification of a small multifunctional molecule followed by DA coupling with a multifunctional maleimide. (b) Modification of a functional linear polymer, or polymerization to obtain a linear furan-functional macromolecule, followed by DA coupling. (c) DA coupling to form a polymerizable adduct.

and hard (isocyanate) segments, thus allowing for healing at temperatures as low as 65 °C. From a broader perspective, DA reaction is a valid reaction for tuning mechanical properties by combining different types polymer networks. For example, Chen et al. [13] blended linear furan functional DGEBA and linear PU and crosslinked them with DPBM in order to reinforce the PU network while preserving its remendability

2.3. Acrylic and other thermosets resins

The linear (co)-polymerization of furfuryl methacrylate (FMA) followed by coupling with bismaleimides, originally reported by Gheneim et al. [37], is still the most used strategy in the design of DA-crosslinked acrylates for coating applications. The wide choice of available acrylate comonomers, combined by free radical [38–40] or controlled polymerization [41–43], facilitates fine tuning the physical properties of the resulting network. While few works reported the use of DPBM as a crosslinker [38,40,43], some aliphatic alternatives like 1,12-bismaleimido dodecane and 1,6-bismaleimido hexane have been shown to enable higher transparency in the final coating [39].

As an interesting alternative approach, furan and maleimide moieties could be incorporated in the same acrylate polymer as reported by Kötteritzsch et al. [44,45] so that the coupling step does not need the addition of low molecular weight bismaleimides. Nevertheless, extra synthetic steps were required, since the maleimide group has to be converted into a DA adduct to be protected during polymerization and then de-protected.

More conveniently, similar to the DA adduct used in the design of PU matrices, Ehrardt et al. synthesized a reversible dimethacrylate crosslinker for a high modulus, UV-curable coating [46]. A bismaleimide with a polyether backbone enabled solventless processing and healing at room temperature, which occurred below the glass transition temperature of the polymer network, as demonstrated by pressing the grinded DA-acrylate coating at room temperature. In a subsequent study by the same authors [47], the embedding of urethane bonds in the linker allowed to significantly reduce the healing time, owing to the synergistic effect of hydrogen bonding.

Melamine formaldehyde (MF) are thermosets with a key role in the manufacturing of plywood as exterior adhesives or as crosslinkers of acrylics in coating formulation. Despite their importance, thermal reversibility has implemented only in a recent work from Urdl et al. [48]. Specifically, a synthesized furan-melamine was coupled with a polymeric aromatic maleimide to form a DA adduct, which was then reacted with formaldehyde to yield the partly reversible network. The resulting coating could be healed at 120 °C by applying pressure.

3. Applications

The convenience of incorporating DA bonds in coatings has been demonstrated for large-scale replacements of conventional coatings, for instance coatings for corrosion protection. They have also been considered for a much more focused goal, such as a protective layer in the field of soft robotics. Here, the thought behind the inclusion of DA for various applications is highlighted, and strategies are discussed for how dynamic covalent bonds are combined and optimized with other material properties.

3.1. Corrosion protection for metals

DA polymer networks have been considered for anticorrosion purposes, for instance to protect the relatively cheap carbon steel in atmospheric (outdoor) conditions, possibly in presence of air, water or seawater. Crack closure is an important aspect in anticorrosive coatings, as it can extend the lifetime by many years by obstructing any aggressive chemical influences. It has been shown that an epoxy- or polyurethane-based matrix embedded with DA linkages offers by itself some anticorrosion properties by acting as a barrier [15]. Yu et al. [34] performed an in-depth study on the effect of the diisocyanate structure in the prepared polyurethanes on the anticorrosive properties. Others have shown that the inclusion of an electrochemically active aniline trimer in an epoxy-based matrix significantly improves substrate protection [17].

The use of nanocomposite coatings, which combine the barrier properties with self-healing, has proven to be successful as well. For instance, Ma et al. [49] have developed a DA based composite containing cerium oxide nanoparticles grown on graphene nanosheets for metal protection within pipelines. A silica-based multifunctional furan with bismaleimide was incorporated to facilitate the self-healing feature, which together resulted in a near infrared triggered self-healable coating. Wang et al. [50] functionalized cerium oxide nanoparticles with furan groups, which also act as crosslinkers for a maleimide terminated poly-urethane to achieve the same anticorrosive and self-healing properties. Alternatively, hexagonal boron nitride [51, 52], graphene oxide, graphene nano-sheets [53], or halloysite-nanotubes [54] can be used to enhance the barrier quality of coatings to protect the metal for chemical hazards. Inclusion of these nanoparticles improves the coating strength as well, while still having self-healing properties. From these projects it is evident that the self-healing feature of this material extends the service life of the coated metals, facilitated via external heat supply or irradiation. However, the adhesive strength is of crucial for the performance of a coating when it

has the purpose of having anti-corrosive properties. To the best of our knowledge, the use of a primer (to improve adhesive strength), has not been considered yet, even though this is common practice in coating applications today. In metal protection purposes and especially for the internals of pipelines in factories, the resistance of the material towards solvents (besides saline water) is to this point often ignored. Turkenburg et al. [55] did perform swelling tests in the presence of dichloromethane and observed a significant amount of swelling and/or a soluble fraction. It is also conceivable that furan-maleimide coatings fail at temperatures higher than 100 °C with the presence of an organic solvent or oil, since the coating may dissolve based on the rDA reaction that starts to become dominant at these temperatures [56,57]. In the case of outdoor, large-scale application, the question still remains how to apply these coatings on the substrate, since they are often prepared with large amounts of solvent (THF, DMF or chloroform) and via, for instance, spin-coating on a lab scale.

3.2. Interior coatings and flame retardants

The DA reaction can also be included in coatings that have a degree of flame retardance. Flame retardant coatings often consist of nitrogen-rich or phosphorus components. When a fire occurs, these can form a char layer that limits the introduction of oxygen to the vulnerable layer, which in turn stops the fire from spreading [58]. Yang et al. [58] prepared a flame-retarding and self-healing polyurethane, owing to the high phosphorus content in the multifunctional furan block. They proved that flame retardancy can be somewhat decreased compared to the pure maleimide-terminated poly-urethane. In another vein, Urdl et al. [48] proposed furan-maleimide based dynamic networks for the furniture and interior design industry, by demonstrating the self-healing ability and good adhesive strength on wood and laminate surfaces. The combination of these two studies implies that there is a possibility of preparing DA coatings for flame protection of wooden structures or objects.

3.3. Transparent coatings

Furan-maleimide coatings usually have a slight yellow appearance due to the use of aromatic bismaleimides. This feature clearly represents a drawback when a coating is intended for decorative functions or for fabric protection [59]. Moreover, optical materials often require a high transmittance over the full visible range. This feature was achieved by coupling a furan-functional polyacrylate with aliphatic bismaleimide instead of (yellow) aromatic ones like DPBM [39]. Notably, since the transparency and the refractive index matched the characteristics of commercial polymethylmethacrylate, the DA polymer network was used as host matrix for thin-film luminescent solar concentrator [60], a device able to collect and drive light towards a photovoltaic cell. The performance of those devices significantly drops when the film is mechanically damaged and it can be restored by the healing procedure. Yoon et al. [61] introduced in similar highly transparent matrix the option to track down mechanical damages by including a mechanochromic component. As predicted by the authors via simulations, spiropyran reacts to mechanical stimuli and exhibits a purple color and fluorescence at the damaged sites. Visual damage detection can simplify the reparation process of coatings, as it immediately is clear where the coating should be treated. Subsequently the 'marked' scratches can be healed locally by applying a local stimulus, such as heat or light.

3.4. Conductive coatings

DA based resins require conductive additives to impart conductivity. This has been achieved by including metallic nanoparticles, carbon nanotubes or graphene. Lee et al. [62] used graphene in a biobased maleimide-furan resin to improve the conductivity for electromagnetic interference shielding. Alternatively, these materials have been

proposed as recyclable circuit board substrates. Using a highly conductive organic substrate improves the heat management in these devices. As a proof of concept, Chen et al. [52] prepared a composite hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) and a DA-based resin, in which hBN leads to improved conduction within the material. A composite was prepared by dip-coating on a glass fiber, and the recovery of the material was demonstrated by introducing a solvent. This effectively separated the glass fibers from the rest by exploiting the reversible character of the DA reaction. In another vein, Xie et al. [63] proposed a composite of poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT) and a poly-urethane having furan and maleimide groups, and demonstrated its potential as a thin-film electronic material. The main challenge is to balance conductivity of the coating with self-healing ability, since the inclusion of more furan-maleimide functionalized polyurethane results in a better healing performance, but also to decreased conductivity.

3.5. Anti-bacterial

Anti-bacterial properties are very useful in biomedical applications [3]. Wang et al. [64] used a polyurethane mixed with furan-functionalized poly-dopamine for introducing the photothermal effect with NIR light. The furan-functionalized poly-dopamine particles were further doped with silver, since silver-based nanoparticles can have antibacterial properties against a variety of microorganisms. The material exhibited a relatively good strength compared to other DA networks, which was attributed to the introduction of silver nanoparticles. An antibacterial kinetics assay showed the good long-term antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. Zhou and co-workers [65] also produced a DA coating with antimicrobial properties towards the micro-organisms by introducing hexamethylene biguanide to dual self-healing assisted thiol-ene chemistry and DA reactions. Interestingly, they performed a cytocompatibility assay and showed a compatibility of 70 %, which could be considered as weakly cytotoxic. The authors indicate that the inclusion of more polyethyleneimine led to worse cytocompatibility. In general, for biomedical applications antibacterial DA coatings can have a promising future, although the long-term consequences of exposure of cells to dynamic DA networks have not been investigated elaborately. In this context, Zhao et al. [66] proposed DA chemistry for artificial skin and scaffolds for tissue engineering, and the first results (based on the absence of signs of infection or allergic reactions on mice) have shown that after 30 days the inflammatory reaction was not high.

3.6. Soft robotics

Soft grippers are robot components designed to safely handle a wide variety of objects and thus are particularly prone to mechanical damage over time [67]. For example, a common configuration of a gripper entails the use of flexible, silicone elastomer "fingers" controlled with an electrical wire that goes through several chambers containing ethanol. Upon heating, the vapor pressure increases and the chambers start to expand. If the finger is damaged as a result of a cut, the solvent would leak, causing the failure of the actuating system. In this context, Orozco et al. proposed a soft DA-crosslinked coating as an autonomously healable protection layer for the fingers [68]. Terryn et al. [69] instead introduced a pneumatic actuator fully composed on a DA polymer network, able to heal also after structural damages at room temperature [70].

4. Current challenges

4.1. Sustainability

The design and development of novel coatings should meet the increasing concerns for environmental sustainability. Specifically, the following aspects are usually considered: the reduction of volatile

organic compounds (VOCs), the use of renewable materials and the waste minimization [71]. The latter point is indeed an inherent characteristic of self-healing coatings, as they are designed to have a longer service life than conventional ones, provided that mechanical and functional properties are not impaired after the healing procedure.

As for the reduction of volatile and toxic compound from formulations, unfortunately most DA-based coatings are solvent-borne, often THF, DMF or chloroform. These solvents are indeed needed to dissolve DBPM, which, despite its toxicity and difficult processability, is still used as a linker in most of the reported works, arguably owing to its availability on the industrial scale [72]. Few recent works reported the use of maleimides with enhanced solubility in industrial solvents like methyl ether ketone [73] or miscible in bulk with the furan functional polymer [18,46,47]. Alternatively, waterborne formulations have been recently proposed for polyurethane based [29,31,74,75] and polyacrylate DA-based networks [76]. In addition, the synthesis strategy based on DA adducts seems to favor the development of UV (or LED) curable formulations, which enables fast processing [32,33] with low energy consumption and additionally, solventless fabrication [46].

When it comes to renewable feedstock, all major furan building blocks used in the synthesis of DA polymer networks are derived from biobased furfural [77], while the available maleimides are produced from maleic anhydride and diamines. According to Alonso-Fagúndez et al., most maleic anhydride is produced from fossil-based resources, but it can also be derived from furfural via selective gas phase oxidation [78]. A biobased alternative is represented by bisitaconamides, which have been only recently reported as dienophiles in DA-crosslinked epoxy composites [79].

Some recent works have proposed the replacement of the polymer matrix at different degrees of biobased content. Moazzen et al. [80] investigated the use of polyfurfuryl alcohol, obtained from the acid catalyzed self-condensation of furfuryl alcohol, as a functional matrix for DA crosslinking with bismaleimide. The resulting material exhibited self-healing properties and exceptional thermal stability. Cai et al. [81] synthesized a fully biobased polyester via the ring opening polymerization of lactide, succinic acid and dihydroxymethylfuran. After DA coupling with a bismaleimide, the network exhibited self-healing and shape memory. Another cyclic ester, ethylene brassylate, could be also polymerized in the presence of furfuryl alcohol and FGE to yield a furan functional polymer prone to further DA coupling [62]. A similar polyester with a furan group in the backbone was synthesized by Ryu et al. [82] from furandicarboxylic acid and butanediol and then crosslinked with a bismaleimide to obtain a self-healing coating for fabrics. Zhao et al. [83] studied the modification of (plant-based) urushiol (a catechol bearing an unsaturated hydrocarbon chain) with epichlorohydrin. The partly biobased epoxy was then reacted with furfuryl alcohol and coupled with a bismaleimide to yield a self-healing coating. Parihar et al. [84] prepared a multifunctional furan from gum rosin which resulted in a highly crosslinked, self-healing, protective coating after DA coupling. Nevertheless, the final biobased content in the resultant material was strongly reduced by the several synthetic steps employed. Conversely, Turkenburg et al. [55] targeted an acrylate-based coating with high biobased content by copolymerizing diethylitaconate and FMA. Interestingly, the linear furan copolymer was grinded, mixed with bismaleimide, and pressed at 150 °C on a stainless-steel substrate. Healing was performed at even higher temperatures (160 °C), so the occurrence of maleimide homopolymerization or double-DA coupling as side reactions [56,85] cannot be excluded.

4.2. Self-healing assessment and procedures

Many researchers have demonstrated the self-healing ability of the coating, either visually by observing scratch repair or by conducting tensile tests. As Utrera-Barrios and co-workers highlighted in their review, the field is looking for a unified protocol to define the self-healing ability [5]. For instance, the healing efficiency was determined by the

thickness of the scratch after thermal treatment [15,63], the scratch depth [27] or the degree of gloss before and after healing [30,83]. Most studies have used tensile tests to define self-healing efficiency, wherein the efficiency was determined by either the strain at break, stress at break or Young's modulus [25,26,31,35,48,50,53,54,58,64,74,82,86,87]. This shows the general inconsistency of defining self-healing for DA coatings in this research field. Admittedly, reaching a consensus about which self-healing test should be used seems unlikely, since the recovered property that is regarded as important depends on the application. However, a stress-strain curve gives detailed information about the healing performance of a material, even though it is not always clear where the focus ought to be for the application. A combination of tensile tests and another method (e.g. scratch test or hardness) that suits the application would provide comparative information, and also specific details for the practical employment. For the purpose of this review, which includes comparing the different DA coatings, we use stress at break and its self-healing efficiency, because most available self-healing efficiencies were based on stress at break values, and secondly because the stress at break values are more objective compared to the calculated Young's Modulus. Fig. 3a shows the self-healing efficiency of various DA networks, along with the material strength and conditions for the self-healing procedure.

As it turns out, the self-healing ability is in most cases higher than 80 %. However, because of the variety of healing procedures and the time between the self-healing procedure and measurement itself, the high self-healing values between 80 and 95 % may not be comparable, but rather the time that was deemed necessary to achieve this gives more about the material. From Fig. 2, it becomes clear that at higher healing temperatures an increased self-healing efficiency can be observed. One outlier is the work of Ryu et al. [82]. Based on the clean NMR spectra and low tensile properties reported in their work, it is plausible that the material (poly-butylene furanoate) did not cross-link. This is likely due to the electron withdrawing side groups of the furan moiety and steric hindrance, both retarding the forward Diels-Alder reaction.

In general, the stress at break is still comparable with epoxy-acrylates, typically having a value of 20–25 MPa [89]. DA coatings can be very flexible, with reported elongation at break values higher than 500 % [31,74,89–91]. However, a detailed database about other coating properties, such as scratch resistance or toughness is still missing for DA coatings. Diaz et al. [18] went deeper into the definition of self-healing efficiency, and highlighted the importance of the time between the healing event and the measurement of the recovered property. Indeed, a significant recovery of a specific mechanical property might take several hours after the removal of the thermal stimulus needed to visually seal the damage. This time lag, generally not reported, should be then specified as it is crucial in assessing the healing timescale. The healing time at 120 °C has been tested by Truong et al. [26], who found that the self-healing efficiency (based on stress at break) gradually increases by studying the self-healing performance over the 4 h of heat treatment at 120 °C.

Ideally, the damage repair should occur within the application temperature range of the coating. Instead, some studies report healing treatment for several hours at 150 °C [92] or even 200 °C [28]. It should be mentioned that irreversible side reactions, such as maleimide homo-polymerization [85] or double DA, potential aromatization or degradation of the polymer matrix [56] are not commonly considered in the healing procedure, even though these can already occur at 130 °C and above. Moreover, a full decrosslinking of the polymer matrix by retro-DA generally impairs the dimension stability of the coating and might eventually reduce the efficacy of the healing process. Therefore, rheological analysis investigating the occurrence of gel-sol transition at such high temperatures should be provided in order to correctly distinguish actual healing from melt-reprocessing.

b)

Fig. 3. (a) Self-healing efficiencies of DA coatings based on stress at break recovery. The plotted stress at break is the initial material strength of the strongest material reported in the respective article. (b) Infrared stimulated healing in a DA-crosslinked nanocomposite containing 0.4 wt% of indium-doped tin oxide nanoparticles. Micrographs show complete repair of a scratch after 23 s irradiation. Surface temperature reached a maximum of 70 °C. Reproduced from Ref. [88] with permission from Royal Society of Chemistry.

4.3. Alternative heat sources

Heat generation in self-healing coatings is of particular interest since it can reduce the duration of the healing treatment compared to direct heating, and enable localized treatment at the damage site and remote activation for parts difficult to access. Two approaches are generally followed: the photothermal heating and Joule or resistive heating. The latter requires the application of a small voltage from an external circuit on a conductive nanocomposite made from a DA polymer network and carbon black, carbon nanotubes or graphene [93,94]. Differently, the photothermal approach requires the application of Near-Infrared (NIR)

radiation on polymer matrices embedded with molecules able to absorb the radiation and release it as heat. Typically, the healing times are reduced from several minutes to a few seconds. Carbonaceous materials like graphene oxide or graphene nanosheets are typical photothermal fillers for rapid healable DA coatings [49,53,95]. Polydopamine nanoparticles represent a valid alternative since are NIR responsive [64,75, 91] and typically allow for easy post-modification with furan groups, as demonstrated by Wang et al. [64]. This leads to a better incorporation of the NIR responsive filler into the DA matrix, which is expected to prevent micro-segregation. Zou et al. [96] used MXene (2D early transition metal carbides or nitrides) to induce the photothermal effect.

Araya-Hermosilla et al. showed that a sample of furan-bearing polyketones and bismaleimide could be heated up to 140 °C within the order of seconds [88] and could be completely repaired after scratching in 20 s at a maximum 70 °C temperature (see Fig. 3b). This has been achieved by incorporating nanoparticles of tin-doped indium oxide, which, compared to the other NIR active species mentioned above, are transparent in the visible range.

5. Conclusions and outlook

The last decade has seen a growing research interest for the implementation of the self-healing concept into organic coatings, aimed at extending their service life. The self-healing ability can be introduced as a built-in feature of polymer matrix by using dynamic covalent chemistries. Within this context the DA cycloaddition between furan and maleimide is an established platform owing to the versatility and the availability of precursors and the thermal reversibility at moderate temperatures.

Accordingly, DA reversible coupling has been increasingly introduced as an alternative to conventional curing of major thermosets for coatings: epoxies, polyurethanes, acrylics and recently, melamine formaldehyde resins. Regardless of the family of polymers, two trends have recently emerged in the design of DA polymer networks. Firstly, the concept of a fully thermally reversible polymer network, ubiquitous in the early reports on this topic, is being replaced by the design of hybrid covalent networks, where a balance of DA and of irreversible crosslinks is sought to balance adhesion, mechanical stability and healing. Secondly, DA networks are more frequently built starting from a furan-maleimide adduct crosslinker, which is then embedded in the matrix. This is increasingly reported as an effective strategy to protect the diene/dienophile during the network synthesis and to build hybrid networks.

DA-based coatings generally possess good barrier properties and their anticorrosion behavior has been widely investigated. Furthermore, the use of nanofillers has been proved to enhance the barrier properties or enable novel features as antibacterial, conductive or flame retardancy, while preserving the self-healing ability. In addition, some formulations, suitably designed to possess high transparency of selected formulations, could pave the way to optical and aesthetic applications.

Several major issues possibly limit the industrial scale-up of DA-based coatings. Firstly, the synthesis of the precursors, the DA coupling and the final coating fabrication are still processes largely based on the use of solvents. More studies should be then devoted to tackle this challenge by expanding the range of biobased precursors processable in bulk and further investigating formulations as powder or waterborne coatings. Secondly, a standardization of healing assessment is still lacking, owing to the wide variety of healing procedures, based on specific properties. In this context more studies providing a direct benchmark of a self-healing coating against its conventionally cross-linked (or commercial) counterpart are advisable. Thirdly, there is a limited knowledge about the effect of degradation as a consequence of the healing treatment and/or to the environmental weathering. Few studies have contributed to identify side reactions in furan/maleimide networks, but their effect on their performance needs more investigation. Finally, since direct heating as a healing stimulus appears impractical on a large scale and alternative stimuli as photothermal healing appear as a feasible technology to enable faster repair procedures and remote activation.

To conclude, it is believed that the trends highlighted in this review are aimed at bridging the gap towards large scale production, and thus unveiling the high potential of DA-based polymer networks for multifunctional and self-repairable coatings.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Giovanni Fortunato: Conceptualization, Data curation,

Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Paul van den Tempel:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Ranjita K. Bose:** Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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